

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

D5.3 FINAL REPORT ON DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

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Author list

Name	Organization
Attila Némethy	GEO
Catalina Vrabie	GEO

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Executive Summary

This report introduces the AGEMERA project's communication and dissemination (COMDISS) activities within the second half of the project, examining their impact and how they supported the overall project objectives.

In AGEMERA, COMDISS activities have been conducted and monitored under WP5, led by GEO. The communication and dissemination objectives have been as follows:

- Promoting the project's mission to target audiences across multiple channels and using a variety of tools and activities;
- Conveying the project results to relevant stakeholders and end-users;
- Initiating and strengthening collaboration with projects and initiatives that have similar objectives and focus on similar topics.

The COMDISS activities have been carried out with the support and involvement of the project partners in Europe and Zambia. To promote the project and its key results, partners have been taking part in high-level events (conferences, meetings, seminars) on an international level and in their own countries.

There have been several phases to the project's COMDISS strategy. The first phase was focused on raising awareness of the project's mission, its partners, and its planned activities. As AGEMERA progressed, the focus shifted towards promoting the work and results within the different work packages, creating meaningful engagement with target groups, and working towards the widespread recognition of the tools employed or developed by the project, from the innovative technologies and methodologies to the educational resources and survey. As the project approached its conclusion in M36 (July 2025), the COMDISS activities have been aiming to solidify the existing collaborations and pave the way for the use of the project results further (e.g. via the online serious game), thereby contributing to the twin transition goals.

To monitor and keep track of these activities, partners have been filling out a dedicated D&C Excel sheet on a regular basis, including all the details necessary for the Dissemination & Communication sections on the Funding & Tenders portal.

This report will go through all the COMDISS activities carried out between M19 and M36, looking at:

- Communication channels and activities;
- Dissemination materials;
- Publications;
- Events and collaborations; and
- KPIs (Key Performance Indicators).

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1. Assessing the impact of communication activities

1.1 Communication channels

Multiple communication channels were set up at the beginning of the project, taking into account the needs and preferences of the target audiences (i.e. where they would most likely be found) and the COMDISS goals. These channels have been maintained and regularly updated (on a weekly basis or more frequently during active periods) to raise awareness of the project's mission, spark interest in the project results, and build an online community that would act as multipliers of AGEMERA's news and activities, therefore maximising the impact.

1.1.1 Project website

The [AGEMERA website](#) is the core aggregator of all information regarding AGEMERA: from basic information regarding its objectives, consortium, and areas of focus, to the project's key results, educational package, publications, events, and updates. The project website is also the depository of the [AGEMERA online serious game](#), an interactive tool designed to engage users into learning about critical raw materials in a more creative way. The website also lists the projects working on similar issues, with which AGEMERA has cooperated throughout its lifetime, and the newsletter issues that were sent out to the project's community.

The initial structure of the AGEMERA website and its setup were implemented in the first months of the project. By M18, the website was populated with news regarding the various project developments (events, field trips, collaborations). During the second half of the project, the website gained new subpages, in line with the project results. They will be briefly described below:

A) Glossary

As part of its efforts to raise awareness of critical raw materials and the role they play in the green and digital transition, but also to ensure that the concepts the project operates with are fully understood by its audience, a **Glossary** was put together and added to the website. This subpage provides definitions and/or explanations of key terms used in the project, often in their abbreviated form (e.g. SLE – Social Licence to Explore or UNRMS – the United Nations Resource Management System).

Figure 1: Screenshot - Glossary Page

B) Survey

A subpage was also created to include the key information regarding the purpose and results of the AGEMERA survey, piloted in the spring of 2023 in Finland, and later on conducted in four other countries (Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia). The subpage also features the video that was launched towards the end of 2024, in preparation for the Raw Materials Week in Brussels – a video that uses storytelling techniques to encapsulate the different perspectives of local communities on mining activities.

Figure 2: Screenshot - Survey Page

C) Technologies

A subpage was created to spotlight the innovative technologies and methods that have been promoted by and deployed in AGEMERA to pave the way towards responsible exploration. The sections dedicated to each of these (muographic density surveys, drone-based electromagnetic surveys, ambient noise seismic surveys, and the AGEMERA WebUI) explain what they are and what their benefits are, respectively, as opposed to traditional survey methods.

Figure 3: Screenshot - Technologies Page

D) Geo-Suite GUI

A subpage was created to promote the AGEMERA Geo-Suite GUI (Graphic User Interface), a tool developed by OPT/NET and used to visualise 2D and 3D innovative, non-invasive geophysical surveying methods to help quantify the Critical Raw Material potential in the EU. The page also includes two videos demonstrating how the tool works for the Bosnia-Herzegovina and Finland sites.

Figure 4: Screenshot - Geo-Suite GUI page

E) Webinar

A subpage was created as part of the **AGEMERA educational package** to spotlight the webinar for teachers conducted by TalTech at the beginning of December 2025. The page includes the recordings of the two theoretical sessions and the interactive workshop carried out at the end. Also, the page features a couple of testimonials from users who took part in the webinar and hands-on sessions (kept anonymous for data privacy reasons).

Figure 5: Screenshot - Webinar page

F) Workshops

In connection with the Webinar page mentioned above, a subpage was created to gather all these materials for teachers in one place. Therefore, the page links to a) an additional page including all the background information necessary for teachers (a so-called "Teacher's card"), b) the Presentation that was given to teachers explaining the current state-of-the-art and key information regarding Critical Raw Materials, as well as the webinar (with the recordings) and interactive game that was introduced in the previous bullet point.

Figure 6: Screenshot - Workshops Page

G) Critical Raw Materials (CRM) Game

Last but not least, a new subpage was created to introduce the online game on critical raw materials to the audience, featuring a brief description of the game, additional resources, and who it is intended for. The online game is also a separate item on the

main menu bar, being a key resource, and is the subject of a dedicated paid ads campaign, to be elaborated later on in this report.

Figure 7: Screenshot - Online CRM game

GEO made use of Google Analytics reports to monitor the performance of the website and gain a clear understanding of the number of visitors and their profiles, as well as the sections or resources that garnered more attention from the public. At the time of writing this report, the AGEMERA website attracted a number of **12,357 visitors**; the number is expected to increase as a result of the paid campaign dedicated to the online game, but also due to the last efforts in regards to the dissemination of results by the project partners.

Figure 8: Google Analytics Overview

Google Analytics reports also provide insights into the user demographics and journey: how they ended up on the website, which sections were they interested in more, as well as their countries of origin. The highest number of visitors came from South Africa

(showcasing also that the project was successful in spotlighting cooperation between Europe and Africa for sustainable exploration), followed by Zambia, Finland, Ukraine, Germany, the Netherlands, Spain, and Estonia. A significantly high number is also reported for the United States – however, experience has shown that this number may include bots. The majority of users arrived to the website via direct search (i.e. traffic that is untracked by Google Analytics; it could happen when the user types the URL of the website directly in the search bar, when they click on a link to the website with no tracking parameters etc.), followed paid social (generated by two paid campaigns led by TalTech and GEO, respectively), organic search (generated from unpaid search engine results) and organic social (from unpaid content on social media platforms). The most visited pages, apart from – naturally – the Homepage, were the Open Innovation Seminar event page (probably the result of the paid ads campaign led by TalTech prior to the event), followed by the Learning Repository (the Online Game platform), Raising Awareness, Partners, and Blogs, News and Events pages. These results hint to a particular interest in the educational resources developed within the project, the partners behind them, and the progress of the project, as evidenced by the various updates included in the News section.

1.1.2 Newsletter

AGEMERA has launched several newsletters on a regular basis to further engage with target audiences and provide a one-stop overview of all the project activities and updates, as an additional resource to the main project website. At the time of writing this report, **five newsletters** have been sent out to **65 subscribers** via email; a link to each of the newsletters has been provided on the [website](#) and across social media, to further promote these issues among audiences who were not registered subscribers. In terms of content, the newsletters feature different sections: project highlights and updates, news from the fieldwork partners conducted, events the partners took part in, with complementing links to each of the updates and resources mentioned for easy user access.

Figure 9: Screenshot – Newsletter #4 Introduction

What's more, **AGEMERA also coordinated the second issue of the ESMIN (European Sustainable Mining and Innovation Network) newsletter**. This network was initiated by [MultiMiner](#) and counts more than 10 projects working on similar topics related to raw materials and sustainable mining (more details to be found in D5.5). In this role, AGEMERA collected information from all partners and led the editing and launching of the newsletter.

Figure 10: Screenshot - ESMIN Newsletter Introduction

1.1.3 Social Media

At the beginning of the project, four social media channels were launched to support the COMDISS objectives, engage with target audiences, and ensure the widespread awareness of the project's mission, objectives, and results. These channels were [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#), [Twitter \(now X\)](#), and [YouTube](#). These channels were selected upon consultation with the project coordinator and the partners, taking target audiences into account, as well as social media trends (being such a dynamic landscape). A rundown of how these channels performed will be given below.

a) LinkedIn

By far the most successful channel, LinkedIn has proven to be the ideal vehicle for sharing news and updates and building a community with professionals working on or

interested in the AGEMERA mission. At the time of writing this report, AGEMERA counts **904 followers** on LinkedIn, more than 4 times the KPI set out at proposal stage, and one of the highest numbers among projects working on similar topics. This platform has been used primarily to spotlight key results, share updates from the project's work, attract participants for events or promote the participation of the consortium in various events, support sister projects in their communication efforts, and pave the way for the sustainability of the project results beyond AGEMERA's lifetime.

Figure 11: Screenshot - AGEMERA LinkedIn channel

b) Facebook

Facebook as a platform has witnessed a decline in recent years, with fewer and fewer people relying on it as a source of information or news. This has translated into fewer followers on Facebook as opposed to other platforms – AGEMERA has been no exception to the trend. As such, at the moment of writing this report, AGEMERA has **99 followers** on Facebook. However, the platform is still widely used in some countries – including ones in Africa and Europe, which is why the page was kept active, featuring project updates and calls-to-action; a paid campaign has been launched to promote the online game among intended audiences and nonetheless the general public.

Figure 12: Screenshot: AGEMERA Facebook channel

c) X (formerly Twitter)

X (still widely known as Twitter) has also seen a major decrease in popularity in the past year, as a result of concerns encompassing mis- and disinformation, algorithm bias, and data privacy and security, with many users leaving the platform entirely and shifting towards new but similar platforms such as Bluesky or Mastodon. As a result, the number of followers AGEMERA has gained is lower than initially anticipated at proposal stage; however, the platform has been kept active and used as a tool to share project highlights, draw attention to key results, and even conduct live coverage of certain events GEO has taken part in on behalf of the project. At the moment, AGEMERA counts **221 followers** on X.

Figure 13: Screenshot - AGEMERA X channel

d) YouTube

AGEMERA launched its YouTube channel as a depository of the videos developed in the project, including general project videos, videos spotlighting the innovative technologies and methods deployed in the project, interviews and other short videos conducted during consortium meetings, as well as recordings from its events. The channel itself counts **21 subscribers** and the overall view count, at the moment of writing this report, is **715**.

Figure 14: AGEMERA YouTube channel

e) ESMIN LinkedIn account

In addition to its own channels, AGEMERA also has admin rights for the [ESMIN LinkedIn account](#), currently counting **198 followers**. Representatives from each of the projects in the network have this right; AGEMERA has used the account to maximise the visibility of its results, engage new audiences, and reshare project news and calls to action.

Figure 15: Screenshot - ESMIN LinkedIn channel

1.1.4 Social Media Campaigns and Activities

The AGEMERA social media platforms have been kept active all throughout the period between M19 and M36, with regular posts (1-2 times per week on average) aimed at maintaining audiences' interest and boosting the visibility of project activities, showcasing the progress made at different stages in the project. The content was tailored and based on developments in the project (a new result coming out, participation in an event, a particular highlight) or needs at a specific moment (creating momentum ahead of events organised by the consortium, encouraging users to take a specific action e.g. enrol in the university courses, register for an event). Accompanying visuals were created by GEO's design team for each of these posts, following the AGEMERA visual identity to ensure a cohesive image and enhance recognition of the project among audiences.

Figure 16: Collage of social media visuals

Figure 17: Collage of social media visuals

The **#AGEMERAexplains** campaign, which was launched in the first half of the project, continued in the second half with a series of carousels, explaining concepts such as the green transition or responsible mining. The purpose of this campaign had been, from the beginning, to make complex concepts more accessible to people with no prior knowledge of the field. An example can be seen below.

Figure 18: #AGEMERAexplains campaign - The EU Green Deal post

Another campaign was launched and led by TalTech ahead of the Open Innovation Seminar in Tallinn and online, spotlighting the speakers in the event.

Figure 19: AGEMERA Open Innovation Seminar campaign

Moreover, AGEMERA was included in a 5-day social media campaign initiated by GEO on the occasion of the #EUGreenWeek. Each day featured one of the projects GEO is a partner in, specifically dealing with green topics.

Figure 20: GEO #EUGreenWeek campaign

To increase the visibility of the [AGEMERA online game](#) on critical raw materials, GEO launched a paid campaign on its Meta account (Facebook). In terms of demographics, the campaign targeted users in Europe and Zambia, who are working on or have studies in fields related to geology, mining, and mineral exploration. The campaign is ongoing at the time of writing this report; the success of the campaign will be monitored by the end of the project. The campaign visual can be seen below.

Figure 21: AGEMERA Online Game Paid Campaign

At the same time, AGEMERA regularly engaged with content published by sister projects or projects working on similar topics to help raise awareness and contribute to the EU's efforts to support the green and digital transitions. Likewise, the project

partners have been very active engaging with posts (liking, sharing, commenting), which in return determined an increase in the number of followers and broadly speaking, increased the visibility of the project results.

1.1.5 Videos

In the previous report (D5.2), it was mentioned that AGEMERA had launched its first [project video](#), introducing the project mission in an easy, accessible language, following a “problem-solution” approach: detailing the challenges the planet is facing today and how AGEMERA had set about to solve them. The purpose of the video was to highlight the impact the project would have for the average citizen – and how it contributed to a sustainable future. To increase outreach, understanding that part of the project’s target audience may not be proficient in English, GEO, with the support of local partners, uploaded the video in 3 additional formats, with Bulgarian, Polish, and Spanish subtitles, respectively. A dedicated [playlist](#) has been created on the project YouTube channel, and the videos were disseminated across social media as well.

Figure 22: AGEMERA Playlist - General Introductory Video (with subtitles)

A [second project video](#) was produced by GEO in cooperation with UO, focusing on the social dimension of the project objectives. Using storytelling techniques, the video emphasises the multifaceted perspectives on mining and mineral exploration that local communities have, insights that were gained through the work conducted under WP2, particularly the AGEMERA Survey. The video was launched at the EU Raw Material week in December 2024, as part of the first day’s session on “Mining Regions Matter – The Role of European Mining Regional Ecosystems in Implementing the CRMA”.

Commented [JJ1]: launched

Figure 23: Screenshot - AGEMERA second project video

On a different note, to spotlight the innovative technologies and methods used in AGEMERA to uncover the critical raw material potential in selected regions of Europe and Zambia, two videos were produced by GEO in cooperation with the SMEs leading this work. The [first video](#) was developed together with Radai and it showcases the benefits of conducting drone-based geophysical surveys.

Figure 24: Screenshot - AGEMERA x Radai video

The [second video](#) was developed in cooperation with Muon Solutions and it aims to shed light on what muon-based density surveys are, using accessible language (as the general public might not understand these complex scientific terms otherwise), and how this type of surveys benefits mineral exploration.

Figure 25: Screenshot: AGEMERA x Muon Solutions Video

Finally, GEO has also recorded and edited a series of **short interviews** taken with different members of the consortium and Advisory Board during the project's last General Assembly meeting in Tallinn. There are six interviews in total. The interviewees were asked to explain their role in the project and/or their work focus and their opinions on key achievements of the project, in hindsight. The interviews are included in a dedicated [playlist](#) on the AGEMERA YouTube channel and were disseminated across social media, where they were also uploaded organically for better engagement (e.g. the LinkedIn algorithm favours this approach as opposed to linking it to another website, that would take the user out of the platform).

Figure 26 Interviewing Tony Hand from AGEMERA partner TalTech.

1.1.6 Dissemination and communication materials

At the beginning of the project, a set of communication materials was designed and produced by GEO. These materials included a roll-up, a poster, and an A5 leaflet, and their purpose was to help raise awareness of the project's mission, partners, objectives, and planned activities, among the general public. As no tangible results were available at that stage, these materials were used in various events to draw attention to AGEMERA and set the stage for the dissemination of future results, supporting the efforts to build a community around the project. The leaflet was later translated into additional languages to improve accessibility for local audiences (German, Finnish, Croatian).

In the second part of the project (M19-M36), new materials were created to reflect the project's progress and a few small changes that occurred for its partners (e.g. logo changes). At the same time, existing materials were adapted for new audiences (e.g. edits were made to highlight the cooperation between Europe and Africa in preparation for the event in Lusaka), and new ones were created from scratch to suit the needs of

the partners and contribute to the overall dissemination objectives. A short description of these new materials and the adaptation of the old ones can be found as follows.

Flyers

Several new flyers, in different formats, were created in the second half of AGEMERA, ahead of important events and/or to fit the specific needs of the project partners. In preparation for the Living Library event that took place at the University of Salamanca (March 2024), at the end of the 4th General Assembly meeting, a new flyer was produced, including key information about the event (time, location, purpose), and further information about the project (social media handles and website URL, contact information).

Figure 27: AGEMERA Flyer - Living Library event

Ahead of the EU Raw Materials Week in Brussels (9-13 December 2024), and complementing the launch of the second project video highlighting the social aspects of the project's work, a flyer was also designed, printed and displayed at the event, centred around the AGEMERA survey and including key data regarding the number of participants in the survey, the countries that were involved, and the topics that the survey questionnaire touched upon.

Figure 28: Flyers on the AGEMERA Survey at the EU Raw Materials Week (Brussels, 2024)

To continue to help spotlight the non-invasive exploration technologies and methods promoted and tested in the project, a new 4-sided flyer was produced, focusing on the drone-based electromagnetic surveys that Radai had been conducting. The flyer was printed out and distributed by Radai at several events.

Figure 29: AGEMERA Flyer: Drone-based surveys (Page 1-4)

Figure 30: AGEMERA Flyer: Drone-based Surveys (pages 2-3)

Roll-up

On a similar note with the last material mentioned above, a roll-up has been designed and produced to highlight Radai's drone technology that help make mineral exploration more sustainable. The roll-up was later on printed out and used for dissemination purposes in several events Radai took part in.

AGEMERA
radai

Expertise in drone-based geophysical surveys

Tailor-made surveys

- ✓ Magnetic field measurements
- ✓ Electromagnetic surveys
- ✓ Geophysical data processing and modeling
- ✓ Environmental monitoring with wide range of sensors

Benefits of drone-based surveys

- More cost-efficient**
Low start-up, operation and maintenance costs
- Less time-consuming**
Drones can go up to 40-70 line-km per hour
- Less polluting**
We use electric energy to power the drones
- Safer**
Reduced risk for humans
- More reliable and enduring**
A drone can fly over inaccessible areas, can change its flight plan during survey and withstands 5-8 m/s wind

Finnish company **Radai** has been active on the market since 2013, providing fully integrated geophysical and environmental services, from the planning stage to the actual implementation and data processing afterwards, depending on the customer's needs.

At the moment, Radai is testing its novel, drone-based electromagnetic survey system in the EU-funded project **AGEMERA** (2022-2025), dealing with critical raw materials and responsible mining to support the EU Green Deal.

AGEMERA EU Project | @agemera_eu | AGEMERA EU Project | www.agemera.eu

Funded by the European Union

Figure 31: AGEMERA x Radai Roll-Up

Posters

Apart from flyers, several posters were designed by GEO (with the content provided by partners) to support participation in scientific events, boost the visibility of AGEMERA results (and help make it stand out among other similar projects as a result of the use of its distinctive visual identity), and enhance partners' dissemination efforts. Such examples include:

- A scientific poster for TUBAF, introducing AGEMERA with its background, objectives, and benefits for the general public
- A scientific poster for TalTech, introducing the non-invasive technologies tested in the project

At the same time, for the public event led by TUBAF, that took place in early March 2025, a German-language poster was created to announce the event within the premises of the university and attract participants. The poster was designed by GEO, with the text provided by partners at TUBAF. Furthermore, the initial poster created for the university courses led by TUBAF in the spring/summer semester of 2024 was adapted for the new semester (autumn/winter 2024-2025) to attract a higher number of students and spark their curiosity for the green and digital transition.

Figure 32: AGEMERA Poster - Example

Business Cards

In early 2025, AGEMERA was selected as one of the 19 projects included in the EU booth of the PDAC event, a great recognition and opportunity to spread the word about the

project and its result. To support these efforts, GEO designed a series of business cards which included contact information of the project coordinator, Jari Joutsenvaara (who represented the project at the event), and QR codes linking to the main areas of the project's work: the AGEMERA survey, the educational package, the technologies tested in the project, and finally, the general website including all of the above.

Figure 33 Business cards designed specifically for conferences and similar events.

Certificates of Attendance

The second part of the AGEMERA project saw many more events organised by the partners, either scientific events or public events aimed at raising awareness. To reward the involvement of attendees or simply as a confirmation of their efforts and interest shown towards the project, GEO designed Certificates of Attendance, to be edited and adjusted by partners in charge of organising such events. An example can be seen below, which includes a placeholder for the name of the participant, date, and location of the event.

Figure 34: AGEMERA Event - Certificate of Participation Template

1.2 Publications

During the second half of the project another collection of peer-reviewed open-access articles were published by AGEMERA partners. The list can be seen below in Table 1, while the cumulative number of KPI during the whole project is in Table 2 (further down).

Table 1 List of peer-reviewed scientific publications in the second half of the project

Title	Date	Autor/ others involved	PID or Link	Peer-reviewed	Open access
Quantum Leaps in Mineral Exploration: Adapting High-Energy Particle Research for Innovative Geophysical Techniques	2024 Apr	Holma, M., Arancibia, M, Balázs, L., Enqvist, T., Korteniemi, J., Kuusiniemi, P., Surányi, G. & Zare, T., 2024.	https://www.geologica-balkanica.eu/abstract-books	No	Yes
U-Pb geochronology of wolframite from Polski Gradets, Bulgaria and Barruecopardo, Spain, using in situ LA-ICP-MS technique.	2024 Dec	Peytcheva, I. Georgiev, St., Ganev, V., Stavrev, M., Tornos, F., Holma, M.	https://doi.org/10.52215/rev.bgs.2024.85.2.191	yes	yes
Mineral and chemical composition of the high-sulfidation	2024 Dec	Dimitrova, D., Stefanova, E., Hikov, A., Georgiev, S., Peytcheva, I., Stoilov,	https://doi.org/10.52215/rev.bgs.2024.85.2.88	Yes	Yes

epithermal Cu-V-Sn-As assemblage in the Assarel porphyry copper deposit, Central Srednogie		V., Ivanov, D., Stavrev, M.			
Assessment of Near-Surface Geophysical Methods Used to Discover Karst Bauxite Deposits in the Dinarides Using the Example of Posušje Area, Bosnia and Herzegovina	2024 Apr	Šumanovac, Franjo; Kapuralić, Josipa; Pavičić, Ivica; Perković, Luka	https://www.mdpi.com/2075-163X/14/4/378	Yes	Yes
Potential for restoration of biodiversity in karstic mining regions with small-scale mining sites: birds and pits	2024 Apr	Grbeš Babić, Anamarija; Dokoza, Vanda; Lukač, Gordan; Bilić, Šime	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s41207-024-00488-1	Yes	Yes
Louhi - Novel Drone-Based Electromagnetic Survey System	2024 Sep	Markku Pirttijärvi, Pekka Korkeakangas, Ari Saartenoja	https://www.earthdoc.org/content/papers/10.3997/2214-4609.202420098	Yes	Yes
Exploration of karst bauxite deposits in the Dinarides using ground geophysical methods - possibilities and limitations	2025 May	Šumanovac, Franjo; Kapuralić, Josipa; Perković, Luka; Grbeš Babić, Anamarija	https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU25/EGU25-1638.html	Yes	Yes
Empowering Community Engagements: Knowledge and Sustainable Management of Critical Raw Materials	2025 Feb	Md Ariful Islam, Georg Meissner, Jari Joutsenvaara, Karin Käär, Marcin Szumny, Catalina Vrabie, Ossi Kotavaara, Leena Suopajärvi, Helmut Mischo	https://store.smenet.org/23c8kse/287	Yes	Yes
Application of machine learning for fast detection of karst bauxite deposits based on synthetic geophysical models	2025 May	Kapuralić, Josipa; Perković, Luka; Šumanovac, Franjo	https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU25/EGU25-1638.html	Yes	Yes
The Horizon Europe AGEMERA Project: Innovative Non-Invasive Geophysical Methodologies for Mineral Exploration	2025	Joutsenvaara, J., Holma, M., Kuusiniemi, P., Korteniemi, J., Seivane, H., Marti-Linares, D., Schimmel, M., Casini, G., George Buffett, G., Pirttijärvi, M., Saartenoja, A., Štimac Tumara, B. & Kapustin, I.	https://doi.org/10.5194/adgeo-65-171-2025	Yes	yes
AGEMERA: Integrating Non-Invasive Geophysical Technologies, AI, and Social Strategies for Sustainable Critical Raw Material	2025 Mar	Joutsenvaara, J., Holma, M., Niinikoski, E.-R., Suopajärvi, L., Islam, Md A., Meissner, G., Saartenoja, A., Štimac Tumara, B., Vrabie, C., Nemethy, A. & Käär, K.	https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-5708	yes	yes

Exploration in Europe					
Application of Muon Tomography in Bauxite Exploration	2025 Jun	Holma, M., Balázs, L., Surányi, G., Demók, S. & Kuusiniemi, P.	https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0273513	yes	yes
Mineralogy, petrology, geochemistry and U-Pb zircon age of Upper Cretaceous bauxites from Jajce, Bosnia and Herzegovina	2025	Billić, Šime; Peytcheva, Irena; Georgiev, Stoyan; Holma, Marko; Hikov, Atanas; Pavičić, Ivica; Šumanovac, Franjo; Deljak, Gordana; Kurylo, Sergii; Guillong, Marcel	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oregeorev.2025.106736	yes	yes

1.3 Peer-to-peer exchanges

Partners were active in participating in (or organising) various events where interactions and synergies were formed. These interactions and presentations of AGEMERA objectives and ongoing results were ongoing through the period M19-36, involving various peer groups, like science, industry, or policy. Such interactions took place through different kinds of events, a rundown of which can be seen below.

1.3.1 Participation at conferences

AGEMERA partners remained active in participating at conferences and engaging with the scientific community during the second part of the project as well (see list below). Participation took the forms of presentations, conference papers, and posters related to methods or activities in AGEMERA, with now focusing also on introducing the projects' results. We wish to highlight here the **OECD Conference of Mining Regions and Cities**, a prestigious event gathering key actors across the public and private sectors, academia, civil society organisations, and representatives of indigenous communities. Partners were showcasing AGEMERA's work and key results, particularly in regards to ESG practices (e.g. our surveys investigating local communities' perceptions and fears regarding mineral exploration in the region).

2024

- European Geoscience Union meeting, Austria, 2024
- UNECE Resource Management Week, Switzerland, 2024
- GEOSaxonia DGGV Annual Meeting, Germany, 2024
- Arctic Congress, Norway, 2024
- 11th International Conference on Sustainable Development in the Minerals Industry – SDIMI, Italy, 2024
- European Sociological Association's Congress (ESA), Italy, 2024
- Oulu Mining School 10th Anniversary Mining Summit, Finland, 2024
- MedGU24 congress, Spain, 2024
- 34th Annual General Meeting and Conference - The Society of Mining Professors, Australia, 2024
- National conference with international participation Geosciences2024, Bulgaria, 2024
- Nordic Ruralities -congress, Sweden, 2024

- European Raw Materials Clustering Event, Spain, 2024
- ZIMEC 2024 mining conference, Zambia, 2024
- EAGE Near Surface Geoscience 2024, Finland

2025

- Raw Materials Week 2025, Brussels
- ZIMEC 2025 mining conference, Zambia, 2025
- 35th Annual General Meeting (AGM) of the Society of Mining Professors, Germany, 2025
- PDAC 2025 mining conference, Canada, 2025
- EarthDay 2025, Bulgaria, 2025
- European Geoscience Union meeting, Austria, 2025
- AGEMERA Open Innovation Seminar, Estonia, 2025
- OECD Mining Regions Conference, Finland, 2025
- Exploration of karstic bauxite deposits – Workshop, Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2025
- Goldschmidt 2025 Conference, Czech Republic, 2025
- Raw Materials Summit 2025, Brussels, 2025
- AGEMERA Final results showcase – Innovation, Impact & Zambia – Europe collaboration for sustainable critical raw materials development, Zambia, 2025
- AFRIROCK 2025, South Africa, 2025

1.3.2 Seminars or workshops organised/participated in

Public awareness events were held in Estonia, Germany, Finland, Bulgaria, Zambia, and virtually, employing formats like workshops, seminars, and stakeholder dialogues. These events engaged students, educators, the general public, and industry professionals. A strong focus was placed on inclusivity, open dialogue, and active stakeholder involvement. Survey feedback showed heightened awareness and meaningful discussions, though challenges in sustaining engagement—especially with free educational offerings—revealed the need for improved participant retention and motivation strategies. Notably, the involvement of secondary school teachers and students stood out as a major achievement.

In the second half of the project, partners facilitated numerous events and gained a wide range of experience regarding stakeholder views and social engagement, detailed in D2.4-Final report on questionnaires, developed courses and organisation of awareness events.

1.3.3 Collaboration with sister projects and in cluster events

Ever since the beginning of the project, AGEMERA has been extremely involved in the mineral exploration and mining projects community, leveraging its partners' networks and contacts to initiate and build on different types of collaboration. This has helped with outreach and maximising the visibility of the project among these wider networks. The valuable connections formed in the first half of the project were maintained and strengthened in the second half, and new synergies were born with projects who kicked off their work within this timeframe. AGEMERA is a founding member of a network of sister projects ([ESMIN – the European Sustainable Mining & Innovation Network](#)), has

initiated parallel sessions in major events that incorporated sister projects (e.g. [the European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2025](#) in Vienna), has taken part in high-level events alongside related initiatives (the [OECD Conference of Mining Regions and Cities](#) in Rovaniemi), and has participated in clustering events, precisely designed to connect all of these projects and advance scientific collaboration (the [European Raw Materials clustering event](#) in Seville). However, these are only the tip of the iceberg and the key achievements in terms of collaboration – further details for each of these synergies are provided in **Deliverable 5.5** (Final Report on synergies and collaboration).

2. Key Performance Indicators related to communication and dissemination

To monitor AGEMERA's success in terms of engagement with the general public and the scientific community and industry alike, a set of Key Performance Indicators (or KPIs, in short) have been set out at proposal stage and reiterated in D5.1 (Dissemination and Communication Plan and Visual Identity). **The vast majority of KPIs established in the beginning have been achieved and even surpassed**, with AGEMERA significantly outperforming in some areas of activity. When it comes to some of its key results that came out or were finalised towards the end of the project, dissemination is ongoing at the moment of writing this report. For example, partners have invested a significant amount of effort and resources into the [online serious game](#), which was published in the final months of the project; as such, at the moment of writing this report, dissemination is ongoing, with a paid campaign that kicked off at the beginning of M36, which has resulted in 3,000+ additional website visits already. A full breakdown of the numbers is included in the table below.

Table 2 Project KPIs and -achievements related to communication and dissemination activities, M1-M36.

Tools/Channels	KPI	Achieved by M36
Social Media Campaigns	Twitter followers = 500 LinkedIn group members = 200	Twitter (now X) followers = 221 LinkedIn followers = 904
Project video	3 project videos 5,000 views (YouTube)	11 videos 2,620 views (YouTube, LinkedIn)
Press releases	5 press releases Total PR coverage (including online articles) = 500 ?	7 press releases
Posters	Total posters = 8	Total posters = 14
Publications	Total publications = 18	Total publications = 41
Articles	Total articles = 35	Total articles = 81 (incl. website articles)
CRM Educational Package	Total reach = 10,000 visitors	Total online reach = 9,048
CRM Serious Game	Total reach = 500 game sessions	Total reach = 5199 views
Workshops	10 workshops Total attendees = 500	21 workshops Total attendees = 574

Further details regarding the type of communication and dissemination activities performed, the channels utilised, a short description of the activity, as well as the exact or an approximate number of people reached for each of these activities can be found on the Funding & Tenders portal, under the corresponding tab (Dissemination Activities, Communication Activities), and will be included in the Technical Report.

Table 3 Number of communication and dissemination activities performed during M19-M36.

Category	Number of activities
Presentations at conferences	32
Posters at conferences	14
Participation in activities organized jointly with EU initiatives	10
Participation in other events i.e. meeting, consultation, interview	13
Organization of seminars, workshops, and public events	21
Publications – scientific	41
Publications – non scientific	14
Website news items	67
Audiovisual materials	11
Newsletters	6

3. Conclusions

As opposed to the first half of the project (M1-M18), which was more focused on raising awareness about the project's existence, first of all, its mission, partners, and planned activities, the second part was dedicated to the dissemination of results, as these started to come in. GEO, as dissemination and communication work package leader, and the partners focused on promoting AGEMERA's key results among the designated stakeholders (from research communities and academia to industry and media), strengthening collaborations, and paving the way towards the advancement of knowledge and the uptake of these results, beyond the project's lifetime and up until 2030.

AGEMERA has truly built a name for itself in the field and among other EU related initiatives and projects, having gained a strong following online and considerable attention from target audiences. The KPIs set out in the beginning were achieved and, in many cases, surpassed, which demonstrates both partners' involvement in the recognition of the project among experts and the general public alike, and the need for a project like AGEMERA in the current geopolitical and economic climate. Partners will continue to promote the project and its key results past the project's lifetime, ensuring a high outreach and moving closer to the ambitious goal of reaching 5,000,000 citizens by 2030.

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